

WITH SUPPORT OF DESIGNLAB
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AI4YOUTH ELSALAB

1. SOCIETAL CHALLENGE*

1.1. WHICH SOCIETAL CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED AND HOW IS IT LINKED TO THE UN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND/OR THE MISSIONS OF THE DUTCH TOP SECTORS?

Key enabling technologies such as AI can only be designed in a measurably responsible way, if we involve the youth themselves – directly and via stakeholders (child telephone, KidsRights, WEF Generation AI, etc.) – in AI design and the development of normative frameworks around AI. It is precisely this aspect, co-creating with youth, that we focus on in AI4Youth. Researchers have been looking at the effects of AI technology used by youth for some time. There are clear indications that the moral, communicative, cognitive, and psychological identity development of youth and their relationship to society is influenced by AI technology. The Netherlands is an international frontrunner in the field of AI system innovation, but AI development aimed at young people receives little attention. While the urgency is high: the youngest generations of Dutch society are the most often and longest exposed to all the effects of new AI technology. Investing in meaningful participation of youth as future citizens and 'humans-in-the-loop' in the development of AI is essential for the preservation of public values, a responsible-competitive future of the Netherlands, and an inclusive society.

Youth (8 to 24 years old) are exposed to a growing amount of applications based on artificial intelligence (AI) – at home, at school, and in the public space. In certain cases, these applications

are aimed directly at youth, such as in the context of educational resources. However, little thought has been given to the suitability of these types of applications for youth. Let alone thinking of the influence of AI-driven applications on the development of youth. This is worrisome because AI is omnipresent and youth are playfully and unconsciously influenced, while society has hardly any insight into this. Well-known examples are algorithms in applications such as Tiktok and Instagram. New videos are recommended based on previously watched videos, but under the guise of 'entertainment', these applications collect data for commercial purposes 'surveillance capitalism' (2019, Zuboff). Young people are now included as stakeholders in the social debate about the effects of AI and IoT. Research into the suitability of application and impacts of AI on youth is also growing (Turkle, 20). However, this research is usually based on very small, non-representative selections within individual fields, such as different disciplines within computer science, communication science, philosophy, educational science, psychology, or the law. The youth are mainly seen here as research objects (for example in user studies), and not as active participants in the AI design and AI policy process that could also influence the process. There is a lack of an approach in which young people participate meaningfully (think along and participate in decision-making) about AI-driven applications, norms, public values and rights (digital citizenship), and what their influence could or should be on their experience and their interactions with others. With such an approach, young people would be heard (Art. 12; UN Convention on the Rights of the Child) in the AI debate.

To conduct the necessary transdisciplinary research into the influence of AI systems on youth, in which co-creation is central, an infrastructure is needed that youth, their parents, ethical experts, developmental psychologists, lawyers, computer scientists and AI developers, designers, policymakers, can connect civil society organizations and NGOs. Such an infrastructure is currently lacking. In addition, it is important to test existing (transdisciplinary) methods and to adapt and improve them iteratively. Widely applicable frameworks for AI development aimed at youth and guidance of youth in dealing with AI are missing. There is little insight into the demonstrable positive effects of applications concerning possible negative effects on young people and society, and it is unclear how young people, parents, and carers deal with the negative and positive effects of AI.

The ELSALab AI4Youth brings young people, researchers, designers, social organizations, and companies together in learning communities. We are building on a portfolio of current and new research projects on youth and AI/IoT applications. These projects are positioned within the three primary living environments in which young people develop: 'home', 'school', and 'city' (see box). We regard the projects as 'field labs'. The overarching ELSALab AI4Youth aims to be the common thread between the field labs and to highlight, research, stimulate and facilitate the perspective of co-creation and transdisciplinarity. The results and experiences in the field labs help to refine existing research methods.

Social versus scientific scope

As a starting point for the scientific scope, we take the perspective of young people and the living environments in which young people come into contact with AI systems the most.

We use Bronfenbrenner's ecological model to show how the development of young people is influenced by their interactions with AI in various living environments. Of course, this influence

extends beyond the living environment, but to interpret it, it is necessary to create a framework between the living environments. Because learning and living with young people are inextricably linked (Dewey, 1995), we have opted for formal, informal, and non-formal as the framework for the three living environments in which young people develop in our proposal: at home (informal); school (formal) and city (non-formal). By actively involving young people in the co-creation of AI applications within field labs, we show how youth participation is not an end in itself, but a condition for AI development aimed at young people. We validate the collected insights from co-creation sessions with the stakeholders involved in the living environments/field labs.

The AI4Youth ecosystem contributes to the following SDGs:

SDG 9 Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure

SDG 10 Less inequality

SDG 12 Responsible Consumption and Production

SDG 17 Partnerships for the Goals

1.2. WHAT IS THE VISION, MISSION, AND GOAL OF THE ELSA LAB?

Vision

AI4Youth works towards a Dutch society in which young people are involved on a broad scale, structurally and through co-creation in research into the development and impact of AI systems.

AI4Youth is committed to enabling citizens from a young age and their diverse backgrounds to actively participate in the Dutch AI debate inclusively so that the design of AI systems and the relevant normative frameworks also focus on the development of young people.

AI4Youth makes it possible that young people, with their diversity, individual identity, and individual differences, can contribute to decision-making about AI.

Mission

AI4Youth creates an ecosystem in which the research and development of AI systems can take place aimed at young people, with the central question: What is the influence of interaction with AI systems on (the development of) young people?;

AI4Youth enables young people to participate individually and collectively in the analysis, evaluation, and design of (the impact of) AI systems;

AI4youth offers a platform for AI research in which young people can make their own choices, and feel safe and respected (empowered), without the expectation that they have to adapt to AI-mediated standards;

AI4Youth provides experiences of inclusion to young people by showing that their differences are valuable and enriching for designing AI systems and relevant normative frameworks;

AI4Youth consciously stimulates youth-oriented AI design and AI-oriented guidance for young people in a democratic society in which sustainable public values and AI innovation reinforce each other;

AI4Youth enriches scientific frameworks of ethics, regulations, developmental psychology, computer science, and AI design around young people.

1.3. WHICH SMART OBJECTIVES ARE PURSUED?

Type (amount)	Description
Conference (4)	After 1 year, the consortium has been consolidated and the most important stakeholders within the ecosystem have been involved. Each year, the consortium discusses the progress of the ELSA Lab based on an (openly accessible) conference, based on practical examples in the field labs/learning communities.
Field labs (4+)	The project starts with 3 field labs with learning communities from already current projects, spread over the living environments (home, school, city). During the project, at least 1 additional field lab will be developed for each living environment to obtain the broadest possible picture of the perspectives within the environments.
Workshops (8+)	To shape co-creation with young people within the field labs and to activate learning communities, we organize at least 2 multi-stakeholder (young people, parents, teachers, designers, NGO, libraries, etc.) workshops per field lab.
Publications (12)	Each field lab will produce its field lab-specific publications that provide input for the research in the ELSA lab. We expect each field lab to produce at least 1 ELSA-specific publication, including one on the research methodology (6). We assume that these publications provide the ingredients for at least 6 publications that transcend field lab.
Graduation projects (8)	The field labs offer students from various disciplines the opportunity to formulate graduation projects for their Bachelor/Master theses.
Whitepapers (8)	To broadly inform the ecosystem about the results, at least two white papers will be published on average per year, which will translate the scientific insights for the benefit of the broader narrative within the ecosystem.
Methods (4)	As building blocks for the development of digital citizenship curricula for young people and teachers in primary and secondary education, we develop methods around ethics, law, and societal implications of AI systems.
Frameworks (6)	Sharpening and developing frameworks (regulations, standards, guidelines) for the development and supervision of AI is an important objective of this ELSA lab. We are thinking of things like an Age-appropriate design code or guidelines from the EU High-

	Level Expert Group Guidelines on Trustworthy AI, Children's Rights (UN Convention on the Rights of the Child). It also includes improving tools used in this context (eg Pre-Ethics Tool).
Agenda (6)	The results from the ELSA lab must be included in agendas and roadmaps such as from NL AI Strategy, KIA Key Technology, WRR Opgave AI, and at the European level the European AI Act. We are committed to at least 6 actions from AI4Youth towards these initiatives.
Grant applications (6)	To stimulate the development of new field labs under the AI4Youth banner, but also to perpetuate AI4Youth's activities for the longer term, the lab will participate in applications for national and European research and innovation grants.
Child participation (1000+)	Because the involvement of young people in the research is central, an estimate of the level of ambition is indispensable. Assuming a participation level (on-site and online) of at least 100 young people per field lab, which in special cases (for example research at specific locations in the public space) can rise to 500 young people, we aim to have at least 1000 young people within the ELSA Lab. young people to participate.
Register (150+)	To actively bring the insights, documentation, and frameworks to the attention of the various stakeholders, the ELSA lab is setting up a publication register for stakeholders to disseminate information within their communities.

Existing partner projects (FieldLabs)

Project	FTEs	PI	Partners	Context	Period	Budget
CHATTERS : Kind in Gesprek met Media	2 PhD	Dr. R. Ordelman (EEMCS)	Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid; CLICKNL; SIDNfonds;	CITY	2020 - 2024	500K
CLIC-IT	1.0 Ph.D. student, 0.8 postdoc, 1.0 PDEng, 4*0.2 researchers HBO	Prof. Dr. M.D. Endedijk (BMS)	Saxion University, Hanze University Groningen, Fontys University, and Windesheim University, and 13 learning communities and 10 societal partners	SCHOOL	2022-2026	1M
ACHIEVE - Altering habits from Childhood on,	1 Post-Doc, 5 Junior	dr. J.H.W. van den Boer	University of Twente, LTO	HOME, CITY	2020-2022	51k

promoting Healthy and environmentally sustainable food choices in Interactive Embodied play environments for Vitality and the Environment-	scientific programmer	(EEMCS)	Noord, Mineral Valley Twente, Leussink Retail Group B.V., and collaborations with Groen Kennispoort Twente, BSO de Vlinder; Bonhoeffer College; Educatieboeren			
Navigating the cross-contextual media landscape: Children's and adolescent's digital media use, development and (in)equality NWA project	2 PhD	Prof. Alexander Deursen (BMS)	Utrecht university, Maastricht University, School of Business and Economics (SBE), Research Centre for Education and the Labour Market (ROA), Fontys University of Applied Sciences, Radboud University, University of Twente, Utrecht University, Leiden University, ICLON, Expertisecentrum Nederlands, Windesheim University of Applied Sciences	HOME, SCHOOL, CITY	2023 start	
Youth Skills		Prof. Alexander Deursen		HOME, SCHOOL, CITY		164500
AI Awareness project of children in The Netherlands	Post-doc	Dr. Karolina La Fors	DesignLab, KidsRights	HOME, SCHOOL, CITY		

GoLabz Go-Ga Lab	1 Ph.D. (chatbot)	Prof. Ton de Jong; Prof. Susan McKenney	University of Twente (EU project coordinator)	SCHOOL		
Gen C: Children of 2050	Artist, designer	Bianca Catalog	Tetem exhibition	CITY		
Bumpy Galaxy	Artist, designer	Bianca Carague	Tetem exhibition	CITY		
Bridging Data in the Built Environment	2 PhD	Dr. Michael Nagenborg (project leader - UT)	University of Twente; TU Delft; Amsterdam Metropolitan Institute; MX3D	CITY	2018-2023	476K
Disastrous Information: Embedding “Do No Harm” principles into innovative geo-intelligence workflows for effective humanitarian action	1 Ph.D.; 1 Post-doc	Dr. Michael Nagenborg	University of Twente; UNICEF Malawi	CITY	2021-2024	

2. INSIGHT COLLECTION AND VALIDATION*

2.1. HOW ARE INSIGHTS COLLECTED, VALIDATED, AND DOCUMENTED?

The insights are collected at three levels with field labs serving as use cases that connect the three levels:

- 1) AI field labs:** this is where research takes place into AI-driven applications that young people consciously or unconsciously come into contact with, such as concerning recommendation systems, virtual assistants, and robots. Existing (commercial or open) platforms (eg Instagram) or services (eg Google APIs) can be part of the research here,

but often new applications, techniques, and algorithms will be tested based on prototypes. AI-driven applications consist of various components that can form part of research separately (eg underlying data infrastructure, design interaction, an embodiment of a robot, etc.). This research is positioned within one of the contexts 'homes', 'SCHOOL', and 'CITY'. This research delivers scientific publications, workshops, methods for AI co-creation, white papers at the application level, and algorithms.

- 2) **Co-creation research/methods:** based on the use cases within the AI field labs, the methodology of (ELSA) co-creation with young people is investigated based on, among other things, the Responsible Futuring approach, building on existing co-creation methods. Co-creation with young people focuses on a) knowledge and understanding between researchers and young people about AI computing, ethics, law/child rights, design, and psychology, and b) ELSA skill-building for and with young people. This research produces scientific publications at the level of co-design and design thinking, with and for young people.
- 3) **Social frameworks:** the results from (1) and (2) and the experiences gained here within the social contexts and relevant frameworks (policy, legal, technical, ethical) help to set the agendas (NL AI Strategy; KIA Key Technology), regulations (European AI Act), standards (age-appropriate design code, other NEN standards), and guidelines (EU High-Level Expert Group Guidelines on Trustworthy AI).

2.2. WHICH RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH PRINCIPLES ARE APPLIED?

The insights are documented in scientific publications, position papers, white papers, methodologies for curricula, policy documents, educational materials, design criteria, certificates, and toolkits for co-creation. To actively bring the insights to the attention of the various stakeholders, the ELSA lab will set up a digital infrastructure in the form of a digital and online information register from which the different types of stakeholders can serve specific user groups via their own (online) channels.

2.3. WHAT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH METHODS ARE APPLIED?

The insights from the field labs are examined from two overarching perspectives: how do the insights contribute to (i) general frameworks for the interaction with AI by young people and (ii) AI research aimed at young people? A combination of quantitative and qualitative scientific methods is applied.

Method	Type
AI evaluation and benchmarking	Quantitative
Design methods: Responsible Futuring method; Critical design methods; Feminist design; Speculative design; Co-creative AI design methods such as Peer Play; Design justice; Epistemology design methods; Responsible Educational design	Qualitative
Guidance Ethics Approach; Methods for meaningful child participation Action Research	Participatory

The questionnaires for the co-creation sessions follow the standard procedures of the ethics committee (ethical and children's rights impact assessment).

3. DESIGN THINKING APPROACH. SOLUTIONS ARE DEVELOPED USING DESIGN THINKING METHODS IN A NETWORK APPROACH WHERE TESTING TAKES PLACE THROUGH SUCCESSIVE IMPROVEMENT CYCLES IN RELEVANT PRACTICAL SITUATIONS. THIS IS BASED ON THE BROAD CONCEPTION OF DESIGN THINKING, IN WHICH ALL STAKEHOLDERS ARE INCLUDED: END USERS, SPECIALISTS, TECHNICIANS, POLICYMAKERS, AND ADMINISTRATORS.

3.1 HOW IS A DESIGN THINKING APPROACH USED?

The design-thinking approach is central to all levels of AI4Youth: the young people themselves, AI, and society. The ecosystem of researchers and social partners within the ELSA lab guarantees the safe space and broad scale needed to apply design thinking methods and organize co-creation sessions aimed at young people in multiple phases of the development of AI systems.

In our approach, we use empirical methods aimed at young people, co-design methods, and the Responsible Futuring method. Responsible Futuring enables academics, industry, government, students, designers, and citizens to become more aware of their role in the process, think about the short- and long-term impact of ideas and technologies and come up with solutions for societal challenges. The implementation of the Responsible Futuring approach is supported by the application of the guidance ethics approach (GEA). The

GEA is intended to better map the ethical considerations of various stakeholders and to make them part of scientific and social discussion.

3.2 HOW ARE SUCCESSIVE CYCLES USED?

The Guidance Ethics and the Responsible Futuring method work with four phases with successive cycles, which can be applied iteratively: (1) connecting and relating, (2) understanding and framing, (3) imagining and imagining, and (4) reflecting and reframing. These phases are based on the social problem, in our case the influence of AI systems on young people. The improvement cycles follow the SMART goals and those cycles are applied according to the analysis, evaluation, action, and interaction design phase.

3.3 WHICH STAKEHOLDERS ARE INVOLVED IN WHICH PHASE AND WHAT TASK DO THEY HAVE?

Stakeholder types	Stakeholder	Task	Phase
Youth	Schoolnetworks, Science Hub TU Delft; Leiden University; University of Twente; KidsRights	organisation co-creation sessions	All phases
Civil Society	KidsRights	Platforms for co-creation; children's rights guaranteed	All phases
Scientific	University of Twente; TU Delft; Leiden University; Free University of Amsterdam	analyze; evaluation; design expert; this commission	All phases
Industrial	Dotpin; Ijsfontein; Salesforce	Application of co-creation methods	field lab
Societal	Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Rijnbrink, Nederlands Instituut van Beeld & Geluid	the platform for co-creational sessions	All phases
Societal	Netwerk Mediawisdom & Alliance Digital Inclusion; Nederlands Institute for Sound & Vision; Tetem; Bianca Carague	the platform for co-creational sessions and dissemination	All phases

Civil Society	World Economic Forum Generation AI Platform	dissemination of results	All phases
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4. FOUNDATION BASED ON AI AND/OR DATA. ELSA-LAB PROJECTS ARE AIMED AT MEANINGFUL AND HUMAN-CENTRIC SOLUTIONS WHICH ARE DATA-INTENSIVE & AI-BASED

The data is collected in the co-creative research sessions with young people in different living environments, depending on their age with the consent of their parents or guardians. The data is securely stored and made available for research to the scientists of the AI4Youth consortium network. In doing so, we follow the Data Management Plan advice from the University of Twente and existing legislation and recommendations from the Dutch Data Protection Authority on how to handle research data from young people responsibly.

4.1 WHERE DO DATA COME FROM? HOW WILL DATA BE PROCESSED? HOW IS DATA MANAGEMENT ESTABLISHED?

The data is collected in the co-creative research sessions with young people in different living environments, depending on their age with the consent of their parents or guardians. The data is securely stored and made available for research to the scientists of the AI4Youth consortium network. In doing so, we follow the [Data Management Plan](#) advice from the University of Twente and existing legislation and recommendations from the Dutch Data Protection Authority on how to handle research data of young persons (including age-based differentiation) responsibly.

4.2 WHICH AI METHODS/TECHNOLOGIES ARE USED?

AI4Youth initially focuses on two common types of technologies in the living environment of young people:

- Information Technology: search and recommendation systems;
- Interaction Technology & Robotics: AI-mediated computer interfaces such as virtual assistants or embodied agents such as robots that use one or more modalities (language and speech, visual, 'touch').

4.3 HOW IS THE PROBLEM OF DATA SHARING AND ALGORITHM TRANSPARENCY BEING TACKLED?

We apply the FAIR principles, as indicated in the Data Management Plan (DMP) for research at the University of Twente. During the design and evaluation of our co-creation sessions with young people, we use the [Pre-Ethics tool](#) for researchers. This tool has been awarded the [Juliana Medal](#).

5. QUADRUPLE HELIX EMBEDDING. ELSA-LAB PROJECTS REPRESENT ALL FOUR-HELIX DIMENSIONS. THESE TAKE AN ACTIVE PART AND TOGETHER ENSURE THE PROPER MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION OF ACTIVITIES AND ALSO ENSURE THE ACTIVE INVOLVEMENT AND INFLUENCE OF THE BROADER SOCIAL ECOSYSTEM IN WHICH THEY FUNCTION.

5.1 WHICH HELIX PARTIES ARE INVOLVED?

Based on the quadruple helix idea, the AI4Youth lab implements design thinking together with young people and educators (environment), scientists (academia), AI developers (industry), policymakers (government), and NGOs (civil society).

Academic	
University of Twente	Digital Society Institute; DesignLab; Department of Philosophy; Human-Media Interaction; Department of Educational Science; Human-Centered Design Group; Biomedical Signals and Systems research group; ELAN Teacher Development; Centre for Digital Inclusion; <u>High-tech Business and Entrepreneurship</u> Department; Science Hub UT (Pre-U);
University of Leiden	Science Hub Leiden; University College London
TU Delft	Science Hub TU Delft; Faculty of Industrial Design & AI Tech
Free University of Amsterdam	Law Faculty
Hogeschool van Amsterdam	Lectorship Creative Media For Social Change

Governmental	
Public-private	NL AI Coalitie; AI-Parade

Government	Municipality of Enschede (afdeling onderwijs)
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Societal	
Culture, Musea, and Libraries	Tetem; Nederlands Institute for Sound & Vision & Geluid; Koninklijke Bibliotheek; Rijnbrink
Youth	Netwerk Mediawijsheid; KidsRights
Pedagogues	University of Twente ELAN
Artists	Bianca Carague

Industry	
Youth	Ijsfontein ; Wizenoze
Education	Dotpin
Technology	Mulesoft
General	Leussink Retail Groep;

5.2 HOW ARE THE ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES DIVIDED?

The platforms within AI4Youth, such as the technology-oriented programs, online and educational platforms, school networks, and musea, facilitate co-creation and ensure that youth can be involved in a representative, ethical, and statistically significant way.

Designlab has built up extensive experience in facilitating citizen science in line with the high-tech-human-touch vision of the University of Twente. Designlab is an ecosystem for innovative changemakers and supports connecting scientific and societal actors to work transdisciplinary on societal challenges. Thanks to its many years of experience in coordinating collaboration in a quadruple helix setup, Designlab is an ideal starting point and operating base for the AI4Youth ELSA Lab.

The scientists investigate youth-oriented AI-based interactions from the perspective of education, ethics, legal, or computer science and are responsible for translatable scientific insights, AI-focused curricula for educators and young people, and ethical and legal frameworks surrounding AI designing. Civil society organizations translate insights from different perspectives and provide certifications, policy notes, recommendations, and standards. Industrial parties participate in research and use scientific insights to apply child-oriented AI design and thus implement responsible AI for young people.

The AI4Youth lab as a whole supports inclusive, systematic, and sustainable participation of young people in the process through transdisciplinary AI research.

5.3 HOW IS PROPER PROGRAM COORDINATION AND MANAGEMENT ENSURED?

The DesignLab University of Twente has the expertise and long experience in project program coordination and management. DesignLab is one of the stakeholders in the iterative process of responsible futuring and the joint development of responsible AI. The Designlab is therefore excellently equipped to coordinate and support the program and scientific application of the AI4Youth ELSALab.

6. COMMUNICATION OF FINDINGS IS TRANSPARENT AND MULTI-STAKEHOLDER-ORIENTED. ELSA-LAB PROJECTS HAVE AN ACTIVE POLICY OF COMMUNICATING FINDINGS TRANSPARENTLY WITH STAKEHOLDERS, INVOLVING STAKEHOLDERS, AND ENTERING INTO A DIALOGUE WITH SOCIETY. FOR THE CONNECTION BETWEEN LEARNING, WORKING, AND INNOVATION, ELSA-LABS ORGANIZE THEMSELVES ACCORDING TO THE CONCEPT OF LEARNING COMMUNITIES, IN WHICH LEARNING, WORKING, AND INNOVATION ARE ORGANIZED IN CLOSE COLLABORATION BETWEEN THE QUADRUPLE HELIX PARTIES INVOLVED.

6.1 HOW ARE THE OBTAINED INSIGHTS MADE ACCESSIBLE TO STAKEHOLDERS?

The ELSALab AI4Youth enables an infrastructure and constructive ecosystem among all stakeholders of the quadruple helix. For communication with the various stakeholders, we use the networks of the Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Netwerk Mediawijsheid, Tetem, the science hubs of TU Delft, Leiden and Twente, the VO-HO networks, and the networks of KidsRights. We organize our field labs according to the principle of learning communities. In addition to research and innovation, a community is being developed to strengthen collaboration and in which knowledge sharing and knowledge development with various stakeholders is supported. Examples:

In the CITY field lab, the knowledge and insights from the co-creation sessions around robot interaction in a museum context are made available for the museum kids network and the AI Parade. The Koninklijke Bibliotheek and Rijnbrink from our consortium participate in the AI Parade.

In the HOME field lab, we make the knowledge and insights from co-creation sessions about virtual agents available via the Internet of Things Netherlands.

In the SCHOOL field lab, we will make the knowledge and insights from co-creation sessions about recommender systems available in the network of the National Education Lab, Kennisnet, and Wismon. From the perspective of the overarching (youth-centric) AI research aimed at youth, we combine the insights of the field labs, draw relevant conclusions and formulate

recommendations. We share insights in the network of the NL AI Coalition, Network Media Literacy, and the Dutch Digital Society Alliance. The knowledge from our learning communities around the Home, School, and Citylabs supports and facilitates the objectives of the Digital Citizenship program and cross-school learning and building the Equal Opportunities Agenda. We also share insights from our lab internationally, for example, with the Generation AI Platform of the World Economic Forum and possibly other relevant networks.

6.2 HOW ARE SOLUTIONS PROPOSED AND ELABORATED?

The AI4Youth lab proposes solutions by making ELSA reflections of young people available through co-creation methodologies for transdisciplinary research on AI systems. In the first instance, this will take place within the learning communities of the three Science Hubs, Tetem, and the Rijnbrink library network. Within the infrastructure of these networks, a broad set of schools is reached and interactive lessons are offered in which co-creative ELSA methods are applied.

Solutions are developed by applying co-creation methods. They suffer from building blocks for the development of AI literacy of young people and teachers within (1) the school (PO and VO) and PABO curriculum, (2) the library digital literacy program, and (3) museum creativity and literacy programs through interaction with AI systems. The solutions become scalable because they are translated into building blocks. The building blocks ensure that they make the ELSA co-creation methods around AI systems accessible and easy to implement for both educators and children.

The solutions contribute to developing more child-oriented/suitable AI systems (robots, virtual assistants, recommender systems) for young people. Child-oriented design standards, certification, ethical frameworks, and legal frameworks for AI systems.

6.3 HOW IS THE DIALOGUE WITH SOCIETY STARTED?

The Guidance Ethics and Responsible Futuring approach are inherent in involving society. The core is that there is an approach that supports the dialogue with society, systematically. In practice, the dialogue is organized online and through physical meetings about AI and young people. We use the networks and communities within the field labs and AI4Youth, such as:

The Dutch Royal Library manages the national online youth library, a platform that facilitates research on AI applications in interaction with young people.

Through its network of libraries, Rijnbrink has a lot of experience in approaching citizens and young people in a responsible and design-oriented manner. AI4Youth provides content for the national Digital Citizenship program that Rijnbrink and the Royal Library are enabling.

Tetem as an art platform is an experienced, successful, and transdisciplinary dialogue creators between artists, scientists, schools, museums, libraries, technology developers, and other relevant parties in society. By structurally embedding their creative activities in school curricula, they often stimulate intergenerational discussion in libraries and museums. Their networks and expertise are inspiring for young people and teachers, also around co-creative thinking about AI. KidsRights has a lot of experience and resources to make child participation nationally and internationally accessible and to organize results.

Netherlands Institute of Sound and Vision, Network Media Literacy, Consumentenbond as consumer panel.

7. SCALE-UP AND TRANSFER SOLUTIONS. ELSA-LAB PROJECTS HAVE A RESPONSIBILITY TO SCALE UP SOLUTIONS AND TRANSFER THEM TO SOCIETY.

7.1 HOW CAN SOLUTIONS BE IMPLEMENTED AND SCALED UP?

Youth-centric AI development:

Industrial parties in our consortium facilitate that their AI products are made available for applied AI co-creation methods with various children and other stakeholders and the application of AI co-creation methods takes place in improvement cycles. These AI products are thus enriched by applicable ELSA scientific and social knowledge. Scaling up of these AI products will take place because the industrial parties can market the renewed AI products as child-oriented AI systems. Child/youth-centric AI system development certification Standards at national, European, and international levels

AI-centric guidance of youth (following age-categories):

Robot-oriented lessons and co-creation workshops for educators and young people
Virtual agent-oriented lessons and co-creation workshops for educators and young people
Recommender system-oriented lessons for educators and young people
Input for policymakers to adapt legislation and ethical frameworks and policy around AI that is more focused on youth from the perspective of diverse AI systems.

7.2 WHO IS INVOLVED AND WHAT IS THEIR ROLE?

Stakeholders concerned	Role
PABO	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• introduceren van AI (robot; virtueel agent; recommender system) co-creatie methodes en curricula voor pedagogen; <ul style="list-style-type: none">• introduceren van AI ethiek; kind-gerichte AI en (online) kinderrechten relevante curricula voor pedagogen
Primary-school network; High-school network; VO-HO network;	introducing AI (robot; virtual agent; recommender system); co-creation methods and curricula for educators; introducing AI ethics; child-focused AI and (online) children's rights relevant curricula for educators; primary school network; high school network; VO-HO network; introducing AI (robot; virtual agent; recommender system) co-creation methods and curricula for young people; AI ethics; youth-

	oriented AI and (online) children's rights relevant curricula for educators
Ministry of Education, Culture, and Science	participation-supported AI policy
NEN AI ;	certification & standards for example, <u>IEEE Standard for an Age-Appropriate Digital Services Framework - Based on the 5Rights Principles for Children</u>
Dutch Supervisor on AI and data traffic: Dutch Data Protection Authority	Participation of young people around AI and widely applicable co-creation methods of AI with young people provide input to: legislation, for example; the European AI Act; European Data Services Act, and European Market Act to be amended and youth-informed coordination of policy and supervision

7.3 WHAT ARE THE NECESSARY SUCCESS FACTORS?

Young people feel heard and taken seriously ('empowered') by being part of the process. (Young people can exert more influence/agency.)

By involving them in multi-stakeholder dialogue around AI design and policy the influence and impact of youth participants' agency increases from being only considered as users of these AI systems.

In the social dialogue about youth and AI, meaningful youth participation in research, AI design, and supervision has become a 'sine qua non'.

Fruitful collaborations among a broad variety of stakeholders within and around the field labs enable the scalability of findings through learning communities. The collaboration is relevant, meaningful, and high-quality for each stakeholder (and interesting and simply fun for young people!). The various research disciplines stimulate, enthuse and complement each other and push the boundaries of research so that high-quality scientific publications can be produced.

Industrial Parties appreciate the concrete, applicable guidelines, methods, and clear formal frameworks with which they can improve the quality of their products.

Social parties are happy with the valuable and practical building blocks that they can use in their activities with and around young people.

Governments can rely on the clear outputs of the AI4Youth consortium, such as for policy developments or drafting governance frameworks or agendas and informing regulations and legal and ethical frameworks through youth participation.

